

Process parameter optimization for cutting tool-workpiece interface temperature during end milling of Aluminium alloy 6061 using Taguchi's experimental design

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ABSTRACT

One of the most extensively used alloys in the 6000 family is aluminium alloy 6061 (AA6061). This basic structural alloy is useful for medium to high strength needs and possesses strong properties, making it one among the most adaptable heat treatable alloys. In this paper, optimization of process parameters for cutting tool-workpiece interface temperature during End Milling of Aluminium Alloy 6061 using Taguchi analysis has been presented. The speed, depth of cut, and feed rate are the process parameters / control elements evaluated in the study. Taguchi design of experiments with L9 orthogonal array was used to plan the experimental setting. ANOVA, on the other hand, is used to find the most relevant factors and interactions. An ideal combination of process parameters for machining AA6061 in order to achieve a low signal to noise ratio (S/N) for surface temperature is obtained at feed rate of 20 mm/min, cutting speed of 4000 RPM, and depth of cut 0.6 mm. Feed rate is a significant control measure for regulating surface temperature based on ANOVA.

Keywords

Aluminium alloy, Optimisation, ANOVA, Taguchi Analysis, AA6061

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I. INTRODUCTION

Milling is a basic machining technique that is used to create flat, curved, or helical surfaces, as well as cut threads and toothed gears and prepare helical grooves. The work of determining optimal machining settings is a constant engineering task with the aim of lowering production costs and achieving the required product quality. Superior product quality can only be obtained by having optimal control over control elements such as speed, feed, and depth of cut, as well as better temperature control on the work material. The control on these factors can be achieved by pre examining the observations gathered from the experiment that we have conducted on the work piece AA6061 by using HSS carbide tool type of machining by taking series of readings and finding optimal process parameters using Taguchi analysis to have better control of surface temperature. . Design of experiments (DOE) is an effective strategy for discovering optimal cutting settings based on experimental observations [1]. Cutting tool wear, work piece surface integrity, and machining precision are all affected by cutting temperature, which is determined by the relative movement between the tool and the work piece. To attain better output rates, faster cutting speeds might be employed. Cutting speeds are limited by the development of heat, resulting in lower output rates [2]. The amount of heat produced depends on the material being machined and the cutting parameters, notably cutting speed, which has the biggest influence on temperature. With multiple well-designed trial runs, Taguchi and Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA) may quickly optimise cutting settings. By changing design parameters and minimising the system's sensitivity to source of variation, Taguchi parameter design can enhance performance characteristics. ANOVA, on the other hand, is used to find the most relevant factors and interactions. The specifications of CNC vertical machining and center infrared thermometer shown in (TABLE I, II).

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

According to K.Prasadraju [3], in the cutting process, optimising cutting parameters is a critical tool for improving product output quality while also lowering total production time. Adeel [4] demonstrated that the surface temperature of the work piece may be detected and utilised as an indication to

regulate cutting performance and enhance the optimization process. The Conradie [5] study examines several temperature measurement techniques for determining surface temperature, demonstrating that infrared-based measurements may provide high accuracy and rapid response. Cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut all raised tool temperature, according to Abdil [6], with cutting speed being the most effective parameter in determining temperature rise. The effects of high cutting temperatures, particularly when they are high, are mainly damaging to both the tool and the operation, according to Akil [7]. According to Rahman [8] machining temperatures begin to decline again at a specific cutting speed. This basic study discovered that machining is impossible within a limited range of cutting speeds due to extremely high temperatures.

III. DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Aluminium alloy 6061 with dimensions of 250 x 200 x 20 mm (Fig. 4) was employed as the work material in this experiment utilising a CNC Vertical Milling machine (Fig. 1). In the studies, an HSS cutting tool (Fig. 3) with a tool holder was employed. All of the testing was carried out in a dry environment. The machining parameters of cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut were chosen to investigate their impact on workpiece (Fig. 4) surface temperature. Surface temperature is measured using a noncontact type Infrared based temperature monitoring equipment (Fig. 2, Fig. 5). A total of 9 experiments were carried out using Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array (TABLE III, IV), with various combinations of the levels of the input parameters.

TABLE I
SPECIFICATION - CNC VERTICAL MACHINING CENTER

Manufacturer	Bharat frietz-werner
CNC control system	Siemens 802D
Table size	710mm x 400mm
Transverse(xyz)	510 x 410 x 460mm
Magazine capacity	20 tools
Spindle speed range	60-6000rpm
Spindle motor	Ac 10 Kw
Total connected load	25 KVA

TABLE II
SPECIFICATION-INFRARED THERMOMETER

Feature	K-Type Thermocouple Probe (Bead Type)
Measurement Range	-40 °C to 260 °C (-40 °F to 500 °F)
Accuracy above 0 °C (32 °F)	±1.1 °C (±2.0 °F)

TABLE III
CONTROL FACTORS AND LEVELS

Input Factors	Levels	Symbol	Values
Cutting Speed (rpm)	3	A	1000, 2500, 4000
Feed Rate (mm/min)	3	B	20, 40, 60
Depth of cut (mm)	3	C	0.2, 0.4, 0.6

TABLE IV
ORTHOGONAL ARRAY L9 OF TAGUCHI

Run no.	A (rpm)	B (mm/min)	C (mm)
1	1000	20	0.2
2	1000	40	0.4
3	1000	60	0.6
4	2500	20	0.4
5	2500	40	0.6
6	2500	60	0.2
7	4000	20	0.6
8	4000	40	0.2
9	4000	60	0.4

Fig. 2 Infrared Thermometer

Fig. 3 HSS Cutting Tool

Fig. 1. CNC Vertical Machining center

Fig. 4 Work piece after machining

Fig. 5 Measurement of surface temperature

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

[TABLE V](#) shows the measured values of surface temperature during milling for each of the testing runs.

TABLE V
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR SURFACE TEMPERATURE

Run no.	A (rpm)	B (mm/min)	C (mm)	Surface temperature (°C)
1	1000	20	0.2	32.3
2	1000	40	0.4	32.2
3	1000	60	0.6	32.2
4	2500	20	0.4	31.9
5	2500	40	0.6	32.2
6	2500	60	0.2	32.2
7	4000	20	0.6	32.6
8	4000	40	0.2	31.9
9	4000	60	0.4	32.4

A. Taguchi Analysis

The signal-to-noise ratio assesses how the response swings in respect to the nominal or target value under various noise conditions. Depending on the experiment's purpose, several signal-to-noise ratios are possible. The larger the better type involves maximizing the response and smaller the better focuses on reducing the response to an acceptable level. As our response focuses on lower value of surface temperature, "Smaller is better" can be used to find optimal value using minitab software. [TABLE VI](#) shows the SNR values obtained for the experimental trials.

B. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The findings of the experiment were analyzed using ANOVA, which is a statistical method for discovering factors that have a substantial impact on a performance measure. The ANOVA results with surface temperature obtained from minitab programme are displayed.

C. Discussion

The trials were carried out using Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array, with the results shown in [TABLE V](#). In all of the tests, the surface temperature was monitored. The signal to noise ratio (S/N) is calculated using the smaller-is-better principle, as shown in [TABLE VI](#). S/N ratio is plotted for various process parameters in [Fig. 6](#). Based on S/N ratio two optimum combinations of process parameters were obtained. First combination occurs at Level 3 of cutting speed, Level 2 of Feed rate and Level 3 of depth of cut. Second combination occurs at Level 3 of cutting speed, Level 3 of feed rate and Level 3 of depth of cut.

[TABLE VII](#) shows the results of an analysis of variance ANOVA for surface temperature. The important cutting parameter for impacting surface temperature is discovered to be feed rate (p-value = 0.630). In the range shown in [TABLE VIII](#), changing the depth of cut and speed has a less impact on surface temperature.

Fig. 6 Signal to noise ratio for various process parameters

TABLE VI

SIGNAL TO NOISE RATIO VALUES FROM EXPERIMENT

Run no.	A (rpm)	B (mm/min)	C (mm)	Surface temperature (°C)	S/N Smaller is better
1	1000	20	0.2	32.3	-30.1841
2	1000	40	0.4	32.2	-30.1571
3	1000	60	0.6	32.2	-30.1571
4	2500	20	0.4	31.9	-30.0758
5	2500	40	0.6	32.2	-30.1571
6	2500	60	0.2	32.2	-30.1571
7	4000	20	0.6	32.6	-30.2644
8	4000	40	0.2	31.9	-30.0758
9	4000	60	0.4	32.4	-30.2109

TABLE VII

ANOVA RESULTS FOR SURFACE TEMPERATURE

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Speed	2	0.06222	0.03111	0.57	0.593
Feed	2	0.05556	0.02778	0.50	0.630
Depth of cut	2	0.06889	0.03444	0.65	0.557

TABLE VIII

OPTIMUM LEVELS OF PROCESS PARAMETERS

A (rpm)	B (mm/min)	C (mm)
4000	20	0.6
4000	60	0.6

V. CONCLUSION

The optimal process parameter for the performance assessments of surface temperature for the material AA 6061 was discovered using the L9 orthogonal array, S/N ratio, and ANOVA. The following are some of the study's findings:

- According to the S/N table, the optimal surface temperature value is obtained by lowering the feed rate (20 mm/min), increasing the maximum cutting speed (4000 RPM), and decreasing the deepest depth of cut (0.6 mm). The best surface temperature result was achieved with the greatest feed rate (60 mm/min), highest cutting speed (4000 RPM), and deepest depth of cut (0.6 mm).

- Table feed rate is a significant control measure for regulating surface temperature, according to ANOVA. In the

range shown in Table 7, changing the depth of cut and speed has no influence on surface temperature.

- The results of this experiment show that the workpiece's surface temperature may be detected and used as an in-process signal to modify cutting settings.

- The feed range and cut depth can be increased for improved surface temperature trial results.

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